

Virtual Laboratory for Control Education Using a Solar Collector Field System

Abstract

New educational tools have emerged as innovative approaches that boost student engagement and facilitate a deeper understanding of complex subjects. Focusing on progressing in control engineering education, this work presents the development of a Virtual Lab (VL) designed to teach foundational and advanced concepts in process control. The VL uses a Solar Collector Field (SCF) system as a case study to integrate key topics in control engineering subjects, such as system modeling, Proportional, Integral, and Derivative (PID) control, predictive control, feedforward strategies, and nonlinear control approaches. The proposed system is versatile, which enriches the student experience through widely customizable and realistic simulations. The simulated system, characterized by nonlinear dynamics, time delays, and solar irradiance disturbances, offers students a hands-on learning environment for control system design and analysis. Built using the Easy JavaScript Simulation platform, the SCF VL features an intuitive interface that enhances student engagement. The SCF VL, freely accessible online and on any device (computer, tablet, or smartphone), is a versatile resource for promoting deep understanding and practical skills in control engineering education.

Keywords: Virtual lab, Control education, Solar collector field, Engineering education

List of Abbreviations

ARMAX	AutoRegressive Moving Average with eXogenous inputs
ARX	AutoRegressive eXogenous
CARIMA	Controller Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average
CIESOL	Solar Energy Research Center
EJS	Easy Java Simulations
FBL	FeedBack Linearization
FF	FeedForward

GPC	Generalized Predictive Control
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
MPC	Model-Predictive Controller
MV	Manipulated Variable
PID	Proportional-Integrative-Derivative
PRBS	PseudoRandom Binary Sequence
PV	Process Variable
SCF	Solar Collector Field
STES	Solar Thermal Energy Storage
VL	Virtual Laboratory

1 Introduction

Technological advancements in the past decade have transformed education. In the early 2000s, university classrooms relied on traditional lectures with passive note-taking (Rugarcia et al, 2000). Today, emerging trends like remote learning, virtual, and augmented reality are innovative tools that enhance student engagement and deepen understanding of complex topics (Al-Ansi et al, 2023; Tan et al, 2022; Vergara et al, 2022; Waldrop, 2013). More specifically, practical laboratory classes in engineering disciplines started to change conventional modes of instruction (Koretsky et al, 2008). While effective, physical labs require costly equipment, maintenance, and supervision, limiting accessibility, especially for distance learners. To overcome these challenges, alternative methods like Web-based remote and Virtual Laboratories (VLs) have emerged as flexible and resource-efficient solutions (Mosterman et al, 1994; Woodfield et al, 2005; Barab et al, 2009; Pyatt and Sims, 2012; Guzmán and Joseph, 2021; Chitra et al, 2024; Gavitte et al, 2024; Liu et al, 2024; Chen et al, 2024).

VLs use validated mathematical models to provide interactive, real-time simulations, offering cost-effective, scalable learning while meeting pedagogical goals. Students recognize the importance of real-world experiments (Wiesner and Lan, 2004) but appreciate VLs' flexibility, which achieves comparable learning outcomes to physical labs (Campbell et al, 2002). Web-based VLs further enhance accessibility, allowing students to engage via laptops, tablets, or smartphones anytime, anywhere, making them particularly valuable for distance education (Guzmán et al, 2024).

The need for VLs in control engineering arises from its focus on designing algorithms to regulate system variables (Fadali and Visioli, 2009). Controllers ensure safe, efficient operation while meeting standards (Seborg et al, 2016). This field spans multiple domains, requiring theory and practice, which is challenging in traditional curricula (Heradio et al, 2016a). VLs provide a cost-effective, risk-free solution for testing control concepts across various simulated processes. Below, we review recent literature on VLs for control engineering.

29 1.1 Literature review - Virtual labs for control education

30 Numerous studies have explored the impact of VL across various educational domains
31 (Deriba et al, 2024; Sellberg et al, 2024; Esposito et al, 2021; Reeves and Crippen, 2021;
32 Potkonjak et al, 2016; Alkhaldi et al, 2016). Regarding process control engineering, the
33 key references for VL are detailed in works by Heradio et al (2016a,b); Muñoz-de-la
34 Peña et al (2022); Pereira et al (2012).

35 The use of virtual labs in control engineering has been motivated since 1999, as
36 documented in the report from the International Conference for Control Education by
37 Antsaklis et al (1999). By 2016, more than 40 virtual and remote laboratory initiatives
38 focused on control engineering had been cataloged (Heradio et al, 2016a). From them,
39 novel initiatives have been developed.

40 Carballo et al (2018) discussed the capabilities of a virtual lab for automatic control
41 in a solar tracker system, implementing control algorithms in Mathematica and
42 Simulink/Matlab (MATLAB, 2019). Flores et al (2019) developed a VL for testing
43 various linear controllers on a hydraulic combined-tank system, facilitating control
44 system design and analysis. Guzmán et al (2020) presented a VL for modeling and
45 controlling solar collector fields to teach control skills in various subjects within the
46 Master's program at the University of Almería, Spain. Guan et al (2021) designed and
47 implemented virtual experiments based on a 3D-simulated ultra-supercritical coal-
48 fired boiler-turbine process. Guzmán and Joseph (2021) introduced a web-based VL
49 for process control and design, focusing on an anaerobic digester system.

50 Recently, Vargas-Panesso et al (2023) applied a laboratory methodology for post-
51 graduate students in Civil Engineering, using Matlab/Simulink LiveScripts and 3D
52 simulation to develop control strategies in a coupled two-tank system. Tjahyadi et al
53 (2023) investigated the development of a Digital Twin-based laboratory for control
54 engineering, using a ball and beam system as both a simulated and real-world case
55 study. Tejado and Pérez (2024) presented a VL focused on a wastewater treatment
56 plant case study for teaching process control at the University of Extremadura, Spain.
57 Moreover, Kuhr and Tokaji (2024) introduced a virtual lab for two-tank level control
58 using Simulink/Matlab models and 3D rendering. Similarly, Madani et al (2024) pre-
59 sented an interactive simulator for controlling an inertia wheel's angular position and
60 velocity using a DC motor. Also, Bistak et al (2024) proposed a new architecture for
61 remote laboratories using Matlab/Simulink software to control magnetic levitation
62 systems with 3D visualization.

63 1.2 Scope and contributions of the work

64 Based on the literature review, this work presents a VL specifically designed for pro-
65 cess control education, ranging from undergraduate, master's, and advanced courses in
66 control engineering. The work focuses on creating an interactive, versatile, and acces-
67 sible tool capable of covering both foundational and advanced modeling and control
68 concepts, serving the needs of students and researchers alike. Moreover, the VL aims
69 to offer a high degree of personalization, enabling users to explore diverse process
70 scenarios to study model and control principles.

71 This work advances control engineering education compared to the present litera-
72 ture by focusing on renewable energy systems, specifically a solar thermal plant using
73 Solar Collector Field (SCF) systems. Moreover, it explores various aspects of control
74 disciplines, including nonlinear dynamics, process delays, and persistent disturbances
75 intrinsic and naturally present in the SCF processes. The virtual lab is web-based,
76 making it accessible online for students and researchers. Furthermore, a comprehen-
77 sive user handbook is provided to guide beginners in using the tool, enhancing the
78 learning experience.

79 The objectives are achieved by developing the VL in a web-based environment
80 using the Easy Java Simulations (EJS) platform (Esquembre, 2008). EJS enables
81 the creation of JavaScript-based applications that are accessible through any web
82 browser, ensuring ease of use for users. Furthermore, the VL is based on the behavior
83 of an actual solar thermal plant located at the [BLINDED], focusing on controlling
84 the SCF outlet temperature. Additionally, the natural variability of the distur-
85 bances—determined by the meteorological conditions of the plant’s location—allows
86 for the creation of numerous customizable and realistic simulation scenarios so that
87 students can verify the strong similarities between the behavior of the VL and the
88 real plant.

89 The present work evolves over the contribution presented by Guzmán et al (2020)
90 in several features by including realistic cloudy disturbances, a storage tank model,
91 an ambient temperature model, a Model-Predictive Controller (MPC), tunable Feed-
92 Forward (FF) controllers, identification and modeling tools, performances indices,
93 controllers signals study, reference filter, bumpless transfer, and graphical visual-
94 ization features. The included features are standard in basic and advanced control
95 engineering curricula, and it was based on covering the subjects of the Systems
96 Engineering and Automatic Control Area of the Department of Informatics of the
97 [BLINDED]. Moreover, preliminary results for the tool were obtained through an initial
98 evaluation involving selected students from the Bachelor’s Degree in Industrial
99 Electronic Engineering and Automation and the Master’s Degree in Solar Energy at
100 the [BLINDED].

101 This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 outlines the SCF system used as a VL
102 case study, emphasizing its relevance to renewable energy control and its integration
103 into process control courses. Section 3 details the mathematical modeling and control
104 methods utilized. Section 4 describes the design and user interface of the developed
105 SCF VL. Section 5 introduces the accompanying user handbook for experiments.
106 Finally, Section 6 summarizes the work’s educational contributions.

107 2 The solar collector field process

108 The SCF system in solar thermal plants captures thermal energy from sunlight by
109 transferring solar irradiance to a Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF) within a pipeline. In the
110 primary “hot” circuit, solar irradiance heats the HTF pipeline inside the SCF, which
111 absorbs sunlight and transforms radiation into thermal power. The HTF is pumped,
112 transferring thermal power to a secondary “cold” circuit, where the load machine is
113 located (Camacho et al, 2012). The thermal energy from the HTF can be used for

114 applications such as electricity generation (Alami et al, 2023), water heating for build-
115 ing climate (Castilla et al, 2014), or industrial utilities (Kumar et al, 2019). Due to the
116 intermittent nature of solar energy, especially during cloudy or nighttime conditions,
117 a Solar Thermal Energy Storage (STES) system ensures a consistent energy supply.

118 In solar thermal plants, SCF control aims to maximize thermal energy by
119 maintaining the HTF outlet temperature despite disturbances like solar irradiance
120 fluctuations, mirror dirtiness, or HTF inlet changes. Since irradiance is uncontrollable,
121 HTF flow adjustments stabilize temperature and meet daily power demands. Effec-
122 tive control enhances efficiency, minimizes losses, and reduces reliance on auxiliary
123 heating, supporting sustainability. Additionally, flow rate variations impact thermal
124 power delivery, requiring precise strategies to maintain stable operation and optimize
125 performance throughout the day.

126 The SCF system is valuable for studying control solutions due to its charac-
127 teristics commonly found in real-world processes, offering opportunities to explore
128 several control approaches such as Proportional-Integrative-Derivative (PID) control
129 with anti-windup mechanisms, FeedBack Linearization (FBL), MPC, FF with bump-
130 less transfer, and saturation handling (Camacho and Bordons, 2007; Åström and
131 Hägglund, 1995). Additionally, the SCF supports practical modeling techniques for
132 system identification, such as response curve analysis and model identification using
133 PseudoRandom Binary Sequence (PRBS) inputs.

134 2.1 Case study - CIESOL solar thermal plant

135 The solar thermal plant, serving as the model for the VL case study, is located at the
136 Solar Energy Research Center (CIESOL, *Centro de Investigación en Energía Solar*,
137 in Spanish) at the [BLINDED]. Its primary goal is to supply thermal energy using the
138 SCF system for the building’s indoor climate (Fig. 1). The complete plant description
139 can be seen in the work of Castilla et al (2014).

140 The proposed SCF VL aims to control the HTF temperature that flows out of the
141 SCF system. Therefore, the VL focuses on the primary circuit of the solar thermal
142 plant. The control scheme, illustrated in Fig. 2, includes the SCF and STES systems,
143 excluding the secondary system and other equipment.

144 The scheme in Fig. 2 presents the control system’s main variables, including the
145 outlet temperature as the Process Variable (PV) and the HTF flow rate as the Manip-
146 ulated Variable (MV). Also, it accounts for the inlet and ambient temperatures and
147 global solar irradiance in the collector plane as the disturbance variables. Instruments
148 in the field measure the variables, and the information is sent to a centralized digi-
149 tal computer in the control room, where the control actions will be computed. The
150 control actions are then sent to the pump inverter to regulate the pump velocity and
151 achieve the desired HTF flow rate. The model used for the SCF system is detailed in
152 Appendix A.

(a) CIESOL building.

(b) SCF system installed on the rooftop of the CIESOL research center.

Fig. 1: CIESOL facility. Courtesy of CIESOL, [BLINDED].

153 **3 Modeling and control foundations for the SCF VL**

154 This section outlines the main concepts of the modeling and control strategies devel-
155 oped for the SCF VL. Summarized mathematical formulations, supported by solid
156 literature references, reinforce the approaches' development.

157 **3.1 Process modeling**

158 Modeling is key in control engineering, providing a mathematical representation of
159 system behavior for controller design. The proposed VL models the SCF using the
160 response curve method, which approximates outlet temperature dynamics by ana-
161 lyzing step responses in HTF flow. This approach estimates key parameters—delay,

Fig. 2: Resumed Piping & Instrumentation Diagram (P&ID) of the SCF system used in the VL.

162 time constant, and static gain—essential for PID and MPC design. While effective for
 163 simplified analysis, it is valid only near the operating point. Its practical application
 164 makes it a valuable inclusion in SCF VL for control education.

165 In the SCF VL, insights from the step response method simplify the SCF system as
 166 a first-order response, as shown in Fig. 3. The output is the HTF outlet temperature
 167 $T_{sc,o}(t)$, and the input is the HTF flow rate $q(t)$. The process gain K can be computed
 168 as the ratio between the variation of the system output $T_{sc,o}(t)$ and input $q(t)$ once
 169 the system has reached a steady state represented by T_{ss} and q_{ss} after a step change
 170 in the flow rate Δq from the actual operating point \bar{q} (and corresponding temperature
 171 $\bar{T}_{sc,o}$), as represented in Figure 3. In this way, $K = \frac{T_{ss} - \bar{T}_{sc,o}}{q_{ss} - \bar{q}} = \frac{\Delta T_{sc,o}}{\Delta q}$. In addition,
 172 the time constant τ can be computed by estimating the response curve slope, and the
 173 time delay t_{d_q} can be measured by computing the time passed after the system starts
 174 to react to the input change. Further details about the method can be studied in the
 175 works of [Åström and Hägglund \(2006\)](#); [Guzmán et al \(2023\)](#).

176 The second method used in this work is the PRBS. This method generates a
 177 deterministic sequence of binary signals that mimic randomness, making it highly
 178 effective for system identification based on frequency analysis. Unlike the response
 179 curve method, PRBS can be applied to estimate higher-order models, such as AutoRe-
 180 gressive eXogenous (ARX), AutoRegressive Moving Average with eXogenous inputs
 181 (ARMAX), and state space models, providing greater flexibility and accuracy in cap-
 182 turing complex dynamics. This method builds on the response curve approach by

Fig. 3: Response curve method example of a first-order system.

183 using prior knowledge of the system's dominant and desired closed-loop time constant. It also enables the estimation of disturbance effects, which is essential for FF control design. This includes incorporating signals such as ambient temperature, inlet temperature, and solar irradiance into higher-order models like ARX and ARMAX.

187 In the SCF VL, the PRBS cycle is defined for the HTF flow rate variations, $q(t)$. The signal is generated considering the number of registers n_r and the switching time T_{sw} , repeating itself after a duration of $N_s T_{sw}$, where $N_s = 2^{n_r} - 1$. The spectral density of the PRBS can then be expressed as

$$\phi_q(\omega) = \frac{a_{mag}^2 (N_s + 1) T_{sw}}{N_s} \left[\frac{\sin\left(\frac{\omega T_{sw}}{2}\right)}{\frac{\omega T_{sw}}{2}} \right]^2, \quad (1)$$

191 in which a_{mag} is the magnitude of the PRBS signal and $\omega = 2\pi i / N_s T_{sw}$. This relationship ensures that PRBS effectively covers a wide frequency range of the system output regarding the excitation of its inputs, making it useful for system identification tasks. The details of the PRBS implementation can be obtained in the work of Rivera and Gaikwad (1995); Guzmán et al (2012).

196 3.2 PID controller

197 The PID is one of the control solutions used in the SCF VL. This approach is a control loop feedback mechanism widely used in industrial and automation systems (Skogestad, 2023). Its simplicity, effectiveness, and reliable stability make it a cornerstone

200 of control engineering education. The PID controllers regulate the system output by
 201 measuring the error between the desired output reference (set-point) and the system's
 202 current output. The computation of the control actions is performed regarding this
 203 error, manipulated in three terms: proportional (P), integral (I), and derivative (D)
 204 actions. Regarding the SCF system, to compute the required movements of $q(t)$ nec-
 205 essary to control $T_{sc,o}(t)$ in the desired set-point T_{sp} , the PID control law in the ideal
 206 form is imposed as

$$q(t) = K_p \left(e(t) + \frac{1}{T_i} \int_0^t e(\iota) d\iota + T_d \frac{de(t)}{dt} \right), \quad (2)$$

207 in which $e(t) = T_{sp}(t) - T_{sc,o}(t)$, K_p is the proportional gain, T_i is the integral time,
 208 and T_d is the derivative time, respectively. The PID controller can be extended to
 209 account for the effects of the disturbance in the system outputs by including the
 210 FF approach. While the feedback mechanism is reactive to the disturbances, that is,
 211 only acts when the disturbance has already affected the system, the FF approach
 212 is proactive and can compensate for the measurable disturbances before its effects
 213 are seen in the system outputs (Guzmán and Hägglund, 2024). In the case of the
 214 SCF system, and considering the proposed model described in Appendix A, the FF
 215 control scheme can be included by adding the FF gains and multiplying the measured
 216 disturbance signals (ambient and inlet temperatures and solar irradiance).

217 In the SCF VL, the PID control scheme is complemented by the anti-windup
 218 mechanism to prevent saturation problems with the integral term of the PID con-
 219 troller. This mechanism addresses issues caused by integrating the error when the
 220 manipulated variable is saturated, which can lead to instability or sluggish recovery.
 221 Anti-windup with back-calculation addresses this issue by dynamically adjusting the
 222 integrator state, ensuring a smoother recovery when the system exits saturation. The
 223 adjustment to the integral error is tuned by the tracking constant T_t , which is typi-
 224 cally set to $T_t = T_i$ for practical tuning. Moreover, the PID scheme includes the
 225 bumpless transfer approach, facilitating seamless switching between manual and auto-
 226 matic control modes in a PID controller. It ensures that the transition does not cause
 227 sudden changes or disturbances in the control output, maintaining system stability
 228 and continuity. Finally, the FF scheme is added to the PID strategy, contributing to
 229 minimizing the disturbance effects caused by the solar irradiance variations due to
 230 passing clouds and the inlet temperature and ambient temperature changes. Given
 231 the lumped-parameters model defined to capture the SCF dynamic (see Eq. (A1)),
 232 the FF scheme is set as a static gain for all disturbances.

233 Figure 4 resumes the general PID control scheme with the FF actions used for
 234 the SCF VL. Moreover, further material regarding these strategies is discussed by
 235 Guzmán and Hägglund (2024); Åström and Hägglund (2006).

236 3.3 Generalized Predictive Controller

237 Another widely studied control strategy in control engineering is the MPC approach.
 238 MPC predicts system outputs using past data and future control signals, optimizing
 239 a cost function to minimize deviations from the desired set-point. It accounts for pro-
 240 cess constraints, such as saturation and operational bounds, ensuring feasible control

Fig. 4: PID and FF control scheme.

241 actions. MPC is ideal for complex systems with nonlinearities and disturbances, making
 242 it especially effective for SCF systems, where precise regulation and efficiency are
 243 critical (Camacho et al, 2012; Pataro et al, 2024).

244 In the SCF VL, the Generalized Predictive Control (GPC) approach is imple-
 245 mented as a teaching-oriented version of MPC. GPC leverages the Controller
 246 Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average (CARIMA) model to predict system
 247 behavior and obtain control actions (Clarke et al, 1987). This framework is particularly
 248 advantageous in educational scenarios because it simplifies complex MPC principles,
 249 providing students with a structured and accessible way to explore prediction-based
 250 control strategies while understanding real-world applications, such as those in SCF
 251 systems.

252 Regarding the SCF, the output model is resumed as

$$\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{sc,o} = \mathbf{F} + \mathbf{G}\Delta\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{G}_I\Delta\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{G}_{T_a}\Delta\mathbf{T}_a + \mathbf{G}_{T_{in}}\Delta\mathbf{T}_{in} + \mathbf{e}, \quad (3)$$

253 in which $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{sc,o}$ is the predicted HTF outlet temperature vector defined as

$$\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{sc,o} = \left[\hat{T}_{sc,o}(k+1), \hat{T}_{sc,o}(k+2), \dots, \hat{T}_{sc,o}(k+N_p) \right]^T. \quad (4)$$

254 and k is related to the continuous time t through the sampling period T_s , such that
 255 $t = kT_s$, $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ represents the discrete time step, and T_s is the constant interval at
 256 which the continuous signal is sampled. This relationship allows the continuous-time
 257 dynamics to be represented in a discrete-time framework for control implementation.
 258 Moreover, $\Delta\mathbf{q}$, $\Delta\mathbf{I}$, $\Delta\mathbf{T}_a$, $\Delta\mathbf{T}_{in}$ are the vectors of future increments of the inputs and
 259 disturbances, respectively, being the increment computed as $\Delta x(k) = x(k) - x(k-1)$
 260 and the vector concatenated as in Eq. (4). Also, \mathbf{F} is the free response vector as the

261 free evolution of the system resulting from the past input, output, and disturbances
 262 values (without changing the inputs), and matrix \mathbf{G} is the forced response for the
 263 future inputs increments and \mathbf{G}_I , \mathbf{G}_{T_a} , $\mathbf{G}_{T_{in}}$ are the disturbances response for the
 264 future predictions. Finally, \mathbf{e} is the measured error between the model prediction and
 265 actual system outputs.

266 Once the model prediction is obtained, the following optimization problem is solved
 267 at each sample time to obtain the control actions

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\Delta \mathbf{q}} J, \\ & J = \sum_{i=1}^{i=N_p} \left| \hat{T}_{sc,o}(k+i|k) - T_{sp}(k+i|k) \right|_{\mathbf{Q}}^2 + \sum_{j=0}^{j=N_c-1} |\Delta q(k+j|k)|_{\mathbf{R}}^2. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

268 Here, matrices \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} are the tuning weight parameters to the reference tracking
 269 error the input increments, and N_p and N_c are the prediction and control horizons,
 270 respectively. Matrices \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} can be tuned for each N_p and N_c , although in the
 271 SCF VL, it is defined as one unique value kept constant along the entire horizon. The
 272 form $(k+i|k)$ indicates that the future values are calculated for $(k+i)$ given the
 273 current instant k . In the VL tool, the optimization problem is simplified by not using
 274 constraints, which can lead to an analytical solution for future control inputs in the
 275 form

$$\Delta \mathbf{q} = -(\mathbf{G}^T \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{R})^{-1} \mathbf{G}^T \mathbf{Q} (\mathbf{F}_T - \mathbf{T}_{sp}) \quad (6)$$

276 in which $\mathbf{F}_T = \mathbf{F} + \mathbf{G}_I \Delta \mathbf{I} + \mathbf{G}_{T_a} \Delta \mathbf{T}_a + \mathbf{G}_{T_{in}} \Delta \mathbf{T}_{in} + \mathbf{e}$. If future disturbances are
 277 known or can be modeled, they can be accounted for in the predicted output behavior
 278 from k to $k+N_p$ by incorporating these predictions into the vectors $\Delta \mathbf{I}$, $\Delta \mathbf{T}_a$, and
 279 $\Delta \mathbf{T}_{in}$. Otherwise, the common practice is using only the current measurement of the
 280 disturbances at k and setting future increments to zero.

281 The main GPC control scheme implemented in the SCF VL is presented in Fig. 5,
 282 and further material about the strategy is found in the works of [Clarke et al \(1987\)](#)
 283 and [Camacho and Bordons \(2007\)](#).

284 3.4 Feedback linearization scheme

285 The FBL strategy in the SCF VL simplifies nonlinear dynamics by applying a feed-
 286 back law that linearizes the system, enabling the use of linear control methods like
 287 PID and GPC. This approach helps students focus on designing and tuning linear
 288 controllers while avoiding complex nonlinear behaviors. When combined with tradi-
 289 tional methods, FBL enhances controller performance and provides practical insight
 290 into the interaction between advanced and classical control techniques.

291 The scheme is applied following the structure in Fig 6. The complete nonlinear
 292 equation is substituted by the virtual control signal $v(t)$, provided by the PID or GPC
 293 controller, relating linearly the system output to the control signal as

ZoH - Zero order Holder

Fig. 5: GPC control scheme

$$\frac{dT_{sc,o}(t)}{dt} = f(T_{sc,o}(t), T_{in}(t), T_a(t), q(t - t_{d_q})) = v(t - t_{d_q}). \quad (7)$$

294 Hence, the control input $q(t - t_{d_q})$ is redefined in terms of $v(t - t_{d_q})$ using Eq. (A1),
 295 in the form

$$q(t - t_{d_q}) = \frac{A_{sc}c_fL}{T_{sc,o}(t) - T_{in}(t)} \left(\frac{\beta}{\rho C_p A_{sc}} I(t) - \frac{H}{\rho C_p A_{sc} L} (T_m(t) - T_a(t)) - v(t - t_{d_q}) \right). \quad (8)$$

296 in which $T_m(t) = (T_{sc,o}(t) + T_{in}(t)) / 2$.

297 As can be noted, applying Eq. (8) is not possible since $q(t)$ does not only depend
 298 on the current $v(t)$, but also on future disturbances $T_{in}(t + t_{d_q})$, $T_a(t + t_{d_q})$, and
 299 $I(t + t_{d_q})$, and output $T_{sc,o}(t + t_{d_q})$ - resulting in a non-causal system. Therefore,
 300 the approximation proposed by Roca et al (2009) is employed. For disturbances, it is
 301 assumed that $T_{in}(t) \approx T_{in}(t + t_{d_q})$, $T_a(t) \approx T_a(t + t_{d_q})$, and $I(t) \approx I(t + t_{d_q})$, so these
 302 variables remain constant in a prediction horizon from t to $t + t_{d_q}$. On the other hand,
 303 the future output is approximated with a discrete Euler method, such as

$$T_{sc,o}(k + d_s) = T_{sc,o}(k) + T_s \sum_{i=1}^{d_s} v(k - d_s + 1), \quad (9)$$

304 where $t_{d_q} = d_s T_s$.

305 Hence, the final computed HTF flow using the FBL is

Fig. 6: FBL control scheme

$$q(k) = \frac{A_{sc}c_fL}{T_{sc,o}(k+d_s) - T_{in}(k)} \left(\frac{\beta}{\rho C_p A_{sc}} I(k) - \frac{H}{\rho C_p A_{sc}L} (T_m(k+d_s) - T_a(k)) - v(k) \right) \quad (10)$$

306 The FBL scheme incorporates nonlinear mapping for anti-windup in the PID
 307 controller and constraints in the GPC. By using the inverse of nonlinear dynamics, it
 308 embeds FF action, compensating for disturbances without separate FF control. This
 309 integration simplifies the control scheme, making it easier for students to manage non-
 310 linear systems while applying traditional linear methods. Further studies on FBL for
 311 SCF are available in Roca et al (2008), Roca et al (2011), and Camacho et al (2012).

312 4 The SCF Virtual Lab

313 This section presents the SCF VL tool, describing its functionality and simulation
 314 development using EJS software. It highlights the user interface, experience, and
 315 customization options for users (students, teachers, researchers, and technicians),
 316 emphasizing its adaptability to various SCF scenarios for control education.

317 After preliminary testing with [BLINDED] students, improvements were made,
 318 including fixing visualization issues, adding plant locations, and incorporating editable
 319 features. This collaboration enhanced the tool's usability, resulting in the first version
 320 available online https://w3.ual.es/personal/joguzman/sfc_virtual_lab/.

321 4.1 Software development

322 The VL was developed using EJS, an open-source tool for creating simulations based
323 on differential or algebraic equations (Esquembre, 2008). It simplifies the creation of
324 Java and JavaScript graphical interfaces, enabling platform-independent simulations
325 viewable in any browser. EJS is especially suitable for educators, requiring minimal
326 programming knowledge, and supports interactive multimedia materials, accessible on
327 various devices, including smartphones, tablets, and computers. It is freely available
328 for download at <https://www.um.es/fem/EjsWiki/>.

329 The SCF VL is built on four primary programming components:

- 330 1. **System Dynamics Simulation:** Continuous-time simulation of the HTF outlet
331 temperature, ambient temperature (first-order model), and tank temperature (first-
332 order model) are programmed using the Runge-Kutta 4th-order method. Moreover,
333 a static clear-sky irradiance model generates solar irradiance based on location
334 and local time. This component simulates the evolution of all continuous variables
335 necessary to model the SCF system under realistic and rigorous conditions.
- 336 2. **Control Algorithm Implementation:** The modeling and control algorithms are
337 implemented in a discrete-time version, mimicking actual controller implementation
338 in the real SCF facility. In this formulation, the users are responsible for setting
339 the desired sample time for implementing the controllers.
- 340 3. **Dynamic Visualization:** Real-time graphical representations of variable evolu-
341 tion are implemented to provide clear visual feedback. Additionally, interactive
342 features enhance the user experience by responding dynamically to user actions,
343 such as enabling or disabling specific panels through the VL buttons, streamlining
344 the tool's usability.,
- 345 4. **Data Recording:** Code for storing simulation results upon user request is imple-
346 mented, allowing users to export experiment data seamlessly to applications like
347 MATLAB or Excel. The stored data format ensures that all relevant variables are
348 easily accessible, facilitating further analysis or integration with other tools.

349 Figure 7 illustrates the code's implementation. Black arrows denote system vari-
350 ables, including the manipulated variable, controlled variable, disturbances, and
351 control signals commented in Section 2 and Appendix A. The system dynamics are
352 simulated continuously while the controller interacts with the simulated system in dis-
353 crete sample times. Concurrently, the visualization code reads variables and updates
354 the graphical interface, while a recording function stores variable data in a row vector
355 upon user request. Note that to represent and record VL variables, the Dynamic Visu-
356 alization and Data Recording are developed in a discrete time of 1 s, regardless of the
357 sample time used in the controller. The complete EJS setup mimics typical real-world
358 procedures, providing users with hands-on experience in measuring and controlling a
359 simulated system. Through this formulation, students have practical experience with
360 process control situations like those in industrial processes and SCF plants.

Fig. 7: Programming setup of the EJS code for the SCF VL. Black arrows represent the system variables and controller signals used in the EJS coding.

4.2 Software visualization

The SCF VL's visual interface displays system dynamics and control responses, aiding user understanding of controller effects. Key data such as control errors, reference signals, prediction errors, and FF signals are shown. Users can customize experiments by selecting system characteristics and controllers (e.g., PID, GPC) and setting irradiance profiles. The simulation can model one-day operations with various disturbances and control mode transitions.

The three main panels developed for visualization of the SCF VL are depicted in Fig. 8

The *Main panel* is defined in 6 subpanels as follows:

- **SCF scheme:** This subpanel provides a graphical representation of the primary circuit in the solar thermal plant. System variables are displayed numerically in the current simulated time, while the tank heater is detailed using the heating factor (refer to Eq. (A4)). For simplicity and to reduce on-screen information overload, the control scheme detailed in Fig. 2 is excluded from this view.
- **System variables:** This subpanel presents the variables involved in simulating the SCF dynamics (see Eq.(A1)) and the changes in the temperature set-point. The purpose of this panel is not to highlight precise control effects but to showcase process variables' interaction in a single view. The layout of this panel is shown in Fig. 9.
- **Identification variables:** This panel is dedicated to experiments in *Identification mode*. It allows users to observe how the manipulated variable (HTF flow rate)

(a) Main/Visualization panel.

(b) Experiment panel.

(c) Setup panel.

Fig. 8: Main screen of the SCF VL from a web browser.

383 and system disturbances impact the process variable (HTF outlet temperature),
 384 aiding their understanding of system dynamics for simplified model identification,
 385 for instance, the curve response method.

- 386 • **PID variables:** This panel allows users to monitor key PID controller variables,
387 including the output error and FF signal. Its primary goal is to illustrate the rela-
388 tionship between PID signals and the system’s behavior. This panel is available
389 only when both the *Automatic mode* and *PID* controller mode are enabled.
- 390 • **GPC variables:** Similar to the PID variables panel, this section displays the GPC
391 control signals, such as the prediction error, irradiance disturbance, and reference
392 signals. It is accessible only when the *Automatic Mode* and *GPC Controller Mode*
393 are activated. The layout of this panel is shown in Fig. 10.
- 394 • This panel presents the performance indices used to evaluate controller effectiveness.
395 The selected indices are detailed in Appendix A.

Fig. 9: System variables panel in the SCF VL tool.

396 The *Experiment panel* is designed to give users complete control over the simulation
397 environment. All buttons in this panel interact instantly with the experiment. Users
398 can control the simulation’s progression using buttons like *Play*, *Pause*, and *Reset*. The
399 *Start recording* button allows the user to record the simulation variables for later use
400 with all the logged simulation data. The archive “Virtual_Lab_data.txt” is available
401 for download in the web browser when the user finishes recording. Users can also
402 adjust the simulation *Speed* via a slider and utilize the *Autoscale* button to zoom in
403 and out on control variable graphs for detailed analysis of specific time intervals (see
404 example in Fig. 10).

405 Furthermore, the panel allows users to select the system’s operational mode: *Iden-*
406 *tification mode* or *Automatic mode*. In *Automatic mode*, users can choose between
407 *PID* or *GPC* control while retaining the flexibility to switch between automatic and
408 manual modes at any time.

Fig. 10: Control variables panel in the SCF VL tool.

409 The panel also provides options for setting reference changes. References can be
 410 generated automatically (*Automatically generated* button), based on irradiance levels,
 411 or manually (*Manually generated* button), as defined by the user. Also, a first-order
 412 filter can be included in the control scheme by selecting *Enable Reference Filter* and
 413 defining the proper *Reference Filter time constant*. Moreover, users can introduce
 414 disturbances to the system by manipulating parameters like ambient temperature
 415 dynamics and *Tank heating factor* or using features such as the *Cloud day* button and
 416 *Irradiance attenuation* (see Appendix A).

417 Finally, the *Setup panel* is designed to allow users to customize the system and
 418 controller features before starting the experiment. Users can define controller settings
 419 in this panel, including the FBL scheme, and adjust specific SCF model parameters.
 420 The panel is organized into subpanels as follows:

- 421 • **Irradiance profile:** This subpanel allows the selection of the location of the solar
422 thermal plant, enabling diverse scenarios. Users can specify the *Latitude*, *Longitude*,
423 and *Day*, *Month*, and *Year* to generate an irradiance profile using the clear-day
424 model. For convenience, preconfigured cities and seasons are also available for quick
425 selection.
- 426 • **System parameters:** Users can configure key SCF and tank parameters, such as
427 collector efficiency, heat loss, and time delay. Varying these parameters also allows
428 a wide range of scenarios, affecting the system dynamics and, consequently, the
429 controllers' tuning and performance. These settings are fixed once the simulation
430 begins.
- 431 • **Identification setup:** Users can define the *PRBS* or *Manual* buttons to modify the
432 HTF flow rate to perform model identification experiments. Additionally, PRBS-
433 specific parameters can be customized to generate tailored pseudo-random signals.
- 434 • **PID setup:** This panel enables the fine-tuning of the PID controller parameters,
435 including *Proportional*, *Integral*, and *Derivative* gains, as well as the *Anti-windup*
436 *tracking constant* and FF gains. In addition, users can choose to incorporate
437 or exclude the *FBL* and *FF* schemes. This panel is a key tool for exploring
438 controller performance, allowing users to observe and analyze how parameter adjust-
439 ments impact system control behavior. Once the control structure is defined, the
440 parameters cannot be altered during the simulation.
- 441 • **GPC setup:** This panel allows the configuration of key GPC tuning parameters,
442 such as the prediction and control horizons, weight matrices, and internal model
443 parameters used for the GPC algorithm. Additionally, users can opt for the *GPC*
444 *+ FBL* and FF actions (using the *Disturbance model*). Similar to the PID setup,
445 once the GPC parameters are configured, they cannot be modified during the sim-
446 ulation, ensuring consistent control performance evaluation. This panel can be seen
447 in Fig. 10.

448 4.3 Experiment setup

449 The simulation and experiment setup in the SCF VL is outlined in the flowchart of
450 Fig. 11.

451 First, the user defines key parameters, such as the irradiance profile and system
452 characteristics, providing the plant location and the date on which the experiment
453 will be simulated. These features enable a wide range of scenarios, as variations in
454 the irradiance profile affect control loop disturbances and HTF temperature dynamics
455 throughout the day. Moreover, adjusting SCF and tank parameters alters system
456 nonlinear dynamics, influencing the necessary tuning for PID and GPC controllers.
457 For example, modifying the collector efficiency (β in Eq. (A1)) changes the process
458 gain, while varying tank volume impacts HTF inlet temperature, leading to faster
459 or slower control loop disturbances. This flexibility allows users to explore diverse
460 scenarios and compare controller performance across different system dynamics.

461 After defining the main experiment setup, the user selects the operating mode. The
462 user first chooses between conducting an identification experiment or automatic con-
463 trol. In *Identification mode*, the user can either make manual changes to the water flow
464 or employ the PRBS method, adjusting the parameters of the pseudo-random signal.

Fig. 11: Flowchart of the experiment setup for the SCF VL tool.

465 The user selects and configures the desired controller (PID or GPC) for *Automatic*
 466 *mode*, including options for FF actions and FBL. While controller settings cannot be
 467 changed once the simulation begins, switching between Manual and Automatic modes
 468 is possible. Additionally, it is possible to activate *Bumpless Transfer mode* and observe
 469 its simulation effects for the PID controller.

470 The user can start recording the simulation, which runs from 4:00 AM to 8:00
 471 PM and captures all variables. The recording can be enabled or disabled at any
 472 time. During the simulation, users can adjust references, add disturbances, modify
 473 speed, or pause/resume. At 8:00 PM, the simulation automatically stops, saving the
 474 recorded data and concluding the experiment. The SCF VL allows users to focus on
 475 one control strategy at a time to analyze system behavior and controller performance
 476 in depth. While simultaneously testing multiple strategies is not possible, users can
 477 save simulation data for offline comparison using tools like MATLAB. This sequential
 478 approach mimics real-world experimentation in facilities.

479 5 The User Handbook - proposed experiments

480 A comprehensive User Handbook is provided to guide users through directed exper-
 481 iments and is available on the website [BLINDED]. It helps new users navigate the
 482 SCF VL and conduct experiments aligned with control engineering concepts. The
 483 proposed experiments can be customized, and numerical examples are detailed in the
 484 main document on the site.

485 **5.1 Identification experiment - Response curve and linear**
486 **model**

487 In this experiment, users set the SCF VL to *Identification mode* and configure the
488 plant and system parameters, including location and date, collectors efficiency, heat-
489 loss coefficient, water flow delay, tank volume, and tank heat loss. After starting
490 the simulation and recording, the HTF flow rate can be manually adjusted in the
491 *Identification Setup* panel. The user is motivated to observe the system response
492 and the process variable when it achieves a quasi-stationary point (as detailed in
493 Section 3). Several step changes can be performed, varying the amplitudes of the HTF
494 flow rate changes throughout the experiment. Process variables are monitored in the
495 *Identification variables* panel to analyze the system dynamics.

496 The objective is to derive the linear Laplace domain model $G(s) = \frac{T_{sc,o}(s)}{q(s)}$, observe
497 parameter consistency, and validate results through quantitative metrics. Additionally,
498 it is possible to identify the dominant and fastest open-loop time constants, exploring
499 the influence of the operating point on system parameters for subsequent experiments.
500 An example of the SCF VL's interface is illustrated in Fig. 12a.

501 **5.2 PID and GPC experiment - Input/output control**

502 In this proposed experiment, users use the SCF VL to design a PID controller based
503 on results from the identification experiment. Using a pre-defined sample time T_s ,
504 the user tunes the PID proportional, integral, derivative, and tracking gains, enabling
505 *Bumpless Transfer* while excluding *FF* and *FBL* schemes. After starting the exper-
506 iment, users observe the system's behavior in the *PID variables* panel and assess
507 performance through *Performance Indices*. The user can evaluate controller effective-
508 ness and explore improvements. Moreover, additional analysis can be proposed to
509 assess anti-windup implementation.

510 Similarly to the previous step, the GPC controller can be implemented using the
511 identified system model $G(s)$. The user can tune the prediction and control horizons
512 and weight matrices, excluding the *Disturbance Model* and *FBL*. Moreover, the irradi-
513 ance profile can be altered to study the controllers' performance in different clear-day
514 sky models.

515 The simulation's progression is visualized in the *PID variables* or *GPC variables*
516 panel, and the performances are analyzed in the *Performance indices* panel. The user
517 evaluates controller accuracy, improvement opportunities, and differences between
518 PID and GPC control, particularly noting the GPC's lack of an anti-windup. An
519 example of the PID controller employed in the SCF VL is depicted in Fig. 13a.

520 **5.3 Identification experiment - PRBS and nonlinear model**

521 The user will manage the PRBS signal for system identification in this experiment
522 based on the open-loop model. The goal is to define the PRBS parameters to achieve
523 an effective excitation of the system, considering the system's dominant time constant
524 found in the previous model identification experiment. The plant configuration is first
525 set in *Identification mode*, and the PRBS signal parameters (*Dominant time constant*,

526 *Settling time*, and *Closed-loop factor*) are defined. After starting the experiment and
 527 recording the data, the user will analyze it to estimate the SCF ARX models or the
 528 nonlinear model parameters (β and H , see Eq. (A1)). Moreover, using the nonlinear
 529 model, the user can linearize it to derive relationships between gain, time constant,
 530 and disturbances models in different system's operating points. The PRBS experiment
 531 can be seen in Fig. 12b.

(a) Example of a response curve experiment. (b) Example of a PRBS experiment.

Fig. 12: Model identification experiment using the SCF VL.

532 5.4 PID+FF and GPC+FF experiment - Rejecting disturbance

533 This experiment compares PID and GPC controllers with and without FF control
 534 under normal and cloudy conditions. The FF actions for irradiance, ambient tem-
 535 perature, and inlet temperature will be included by tuning FF gains in PID or
 536 incorporating disturbance models in GPC. Users will evaluate performance regarding
 537 error reduction, disturbance rejection, and control effort. Additionally, they will assess
 538 how the linear model for controllers performs in a nonlinear system with disturbances.

539 5.5 PID+FBL and GPC+FBL experiment - Nonlinear control

540 This experiment focuses on designing and testing an FBL control scheme integrated
 541 with either a PID or GPC controller. The objective is to implement the controllers,
 542 considering the system is now an integrator due to the inverse model. The experiment
 543 involves setting up the FBL scheme by just pressing the check box *FBL* in the *PID*
 544 *setup* or *GPC setup*. The user can evaluate the FBL's impact on disturbance rejec-
 545 tion, control effort, and performance compared to controllers without FBL. Controller
 546 tuning requires prior analysis. The effect of implicit FF control on performance under

547 disturbances is also analyzed. The GPC+FBL strategy is shown as an example in
 548 Fig. 13b.

(a) Example of a PID controller in a sunny (b) Example of a GPC+FBL controller in a
 day using the default system model and the cloudy day using the default system model
 tuning: $K_p = -0,0895 \text{ m}^3/\text{h} \cdot \text{°C}$, $T_i = 1 \text{ s}$, and the tuning: $N_p = 100$, $N_c = 100$, $\mathbf{R} =$
 $T_d = 0 \text{ s}$, and $T_s = 5 \text{ s}$. $\mathbf{1}$, $\mathbf{Q} = 2 \cdot 10^5$ and $T_s = 5 \text{ s}$.

Fig. 13: System control experiment using the SCF VL.

549 6 Conclusion

550 This work presents the development of an SCF VL to teach control engineering
 551 concepts, covering topics like modeling, classical and predictive control, feedforward
 552 strategies, and nonlinear control. The tool offers extensive customization, allowing
 553 students to explore various scenarios. The system's nonlinear dynamics, delays, and
 554 solar irradiance disturbances provide a realistic learning environment. Future work
 555 will address model uncertainties and adaptive solutions for diverse control approaches.

556 The EJS tool has proven effective for designing and deploying the SCF VL. Its
 557 flexibility enables lecturers to create intuitive Graphical User Interfaces (GUIs) that
 558 enhance the user experience. Using JavaScript format ensures the resulting code is
 559 compact, easy to download, and compatible with any device (computer, tablet, or
 560 smartphone) through the browser environment. This versatility allows the SCF VL to
 561 be accessed anytime, anywhere—even offline—broadening its accessibility and practical
 562 use for students. Additional feedback will be obtained in the future from students
 563 in other courses with the idea of improving aspects of the VL and the activities that
 564 can be carried out with it.

Table A1: SCF model parameters. * These parameters can be modified by the user in the SCF VL tool within the defined range.

Parameter	Description	Unit
A_{sc}	Collectors pipe cross-section area	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2$
c_f	Conversion factor	10·3600 s/h
C_p	Specific heat capacity of the water	4186 J/(kg·°C)
H^*	Global heat losses coefficient	[5 - 200] W/°C
L	Equivalent absorber tube length	46.6 m
β^*	Irradiance efficiency factor	[0.1 - 0.9] m
ρ	Water density	972 kg/m ³
t_{d_q}	HTF flow rate delay	38 s

565 Appendix A System models and performance 566 indices

567 A nonlinear lumped-parameters model is used to represent the dynamic of the HTF
568 outlet temperature of the SCF (Camacho et al, 2012). The HTF outlet temperature
569 evolution is represented by the differential equation

$$\frac{dT_{sc,o}(t)}{dt} = \frac{\beta}{\rho \cdot C_p \cdot A_{sc}} \cdot I(t) - \frac{H}{\rho \cdot C_p \cdot A_{sc} \cdot L} \cdot \left(\frac{T_{sc,o}(t) + T_{in}(t)}{2} - T_a(t) \right) - \frac{q(t - t_{d_q})}{A_{sc} \cdot c_f} \cdot \frac{T_{sc,o}(t) - T_{in}(t)}{L}. \quad (\text{A1})$$

570 Here, $T_{sc,o}(t)$ [°C] represents the HTF outlet temperature (PV), and $q(t)$ [m³/h]
571 denotes the HTF flow rate (MV). The system disturbances include the HTF inlet
572 temperature $T_{in}(t)$ [°C], the global solar irradiance in the plane of the collector $I(t)$
573 [W/m²], and the ambient temperature $T_a(t)$ [°C]. For simplicity, this work primarily
574 considers the time delay t_{d_q} associated with the HTF flow rate, although irradiance
575 and inlet temperature delays can also be incorporated (Ampuño et al, 2019).

576 The model parameters β , H , A_{sc} , C_p , ρ , L , and c_f are detailed in Table A1, in
577 which the main parameter are borrowed from the work of Pataro et al (2023).

578 The irradiance clear-day model simulates the solar global irradiance incident in
579 the SCFs. This model is a mathematical representation used to estimate the solar
580 radiation reaching the Earth's surface under cloudless sky conditions, considering
581 atmospheric factors like air mass, turbidity, and the sun's position throughout the
582 day. The goal is to represent solar irradiance as simulated time passes, representing
583 changes in the global irradiance variable $I(t)$ in the Eq. (A1) model. Further details
584 of the static model can be found in the work of Antonanzas-Torres et al (2019).

585 The static clear-day solar irradiance model is extended to simulate a cloudy-day
586 scenario, including stochastic variability representing passing clouds. This is achieved
587 by introducing random attenuation to global irradiance $I(t)$. The methodology dynam-
588 ically modifies the irradiance based on discrete time steps and attenuation factors,
589 including

- 590 • Random Cloud Impact: A random scaling factor is applied periodically to simulate
591 the effect of clouds;
- 592 • Smoothing Transition: A weighted average ensures a gradual transition between
593 changes to avoid abrupt irradiance fluctuations.

594 Let $I_{\text{clear}}(k)$ represent the global irradiance under clear-day conditions. The cloudy
595 day model modifies $I_{\text{clear}}(k)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{if } \text{mod}(k, T_{s,\text{cloud}}) = 0, & \quad I_{\text{cloud}}(k) = I_{\text{clear}}(k) \cdot (0.5 + \text{rand}(0, 0.5)), \\ \text{else} & \quad I_{\text{smooth}}(k) = \alpha \cdot (I_{\text{cloud}}(k) - I_{\text{smooth}}(k-1)) + I_{\text{smooth}}(k-1), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A2})$$

596 where $T_{s,\text{cloud}}$ is the time interval for applying new random attenuation, $\text{rand}(a, b)$
597 generates a random value between a and b , and α is a smoothing factor (e.g., 0.01).

598 Finally, the irradiance is further attenuated by a choosing factor A_{cloud} . This atten-
599 uation can provoke a step change in the irradiance that, although it is not perfectly
600 real, represents additional effects that are very useful to evaluate the FF control action.

$$I(k) = K_{\text{cloud}}(k) \cdot I_{\text{smooth}}(k), \quad (\text{A3})$$

601 in which K_{cloud} is a user-defined attenuation constant between 0.5 and 1.

602 The ambient temperature dynamic is modeled as a function of solar irradiance,
603 reflecting how temperature gradually increases as midday approaches and decreases
604 as the sun sets. This dynamic is represented in the SCF VL by the equation

$$\frac{dT_a(t)}{dt} = (I(t) \cdot F_{T_a}(t) \cdot K_{T_a} - T_a(t)) \cdot \tau_{T_a}, \quad (\text{A4})$$

605 for K_{T_a} represents the proportionality between irradiance and the ambient tempera-
606 ture response, F_{T_a} represents the user-defined factor between 0.1 and 1 for disturbance
607 purposes and can be changed at any time during the simulation, and τ_{T_a} is the time
608 constant, for instance, $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ s.

609 The STES tank model is adapted from the CIESOL thermal plant as described
610 by [Pataro et al \(2022\)](#). The governing equation is

$$\frac{dT_{tq}(t)}{dt} = \frac{q(t) \cdot (T_{sc,o}(t) - T_{tq}(t))}{3600 \cdot V} + \frac{F_{T_{tk}}(t) - 1}{V \cdot K_{T_{tk}}} - \frac{H_{tk} \cdot S_{tk} \cdot (T_{tq}(t) - T_a(t))}{\rho \cdot C_p \cdot V}. \quad (\text{A5})$$

611 The STES tank parameters are defined in Table A2. Note that the factor $F_{T_{tk}}$ can
612 be altered anytime during the simulation.

613 As can be seen in Figure 8a, since the proposed plant model does not consider any
614 heat-loss from the tank to the SCF, the tank outlet temperature becomes the SCF
615 inlet temperatures, so $T_{tq} = T_{in}$.

616 Finally, the proposed performance indices, absolute error (AE), control incre-
617 ments (CI), and compromise index (J_T), are included in the SCF VL to evaluate the
618 controllers. The indices computation is described as follows

Table A2: STES tank model parameters. *These parameters can be modified by the user in the SCF VL tool within the defined range.

Parameter	Description	Unit
V^*	Tank volume	[2 - 50] m ³
$F_{T,k}^*$	Heating coefficient factor	[1 - 3]
$K_{T,k}$	Heating gain	5000 s/(°C)
$S_{t,k}$	Tank surface area	12 m ²
$H_{t,k}^*$	Tank thermal loss coefficient	[1 - 50] W/°C

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{SAE} &= \sum_{k=1}^N \text{AE}(k), \\
 \text{SCI} &= \sum_{k=1}^N \text{CI}(k), \\
 J_T &= \text{AE}(k)^2 + \text{CI}(k)^2,
 \end{aligned} \tag{A6}$$

619

620 in which $\text{AE}(k) = |T_{sp}(k) - T_{sc,o}(k)|$, $\text{CI}(k) = |\Delta q(k)| = |q(k) - q(k-1)|$, and N the
621 total number of samples.

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